

Population Dynamics and Land Use Characterization in Ikot Ekpene LGA, Nigeria.

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Abstract

The land use of Ikot Ekpene LGA was characterized into four classes namely; water bodies, thick forest, farm lands and built up areas. This classification was done through the supervised image classification module of ArcGis on the LandSat Imagery of the Study Area. The area was demarcated into eleven (11) political wards, and the population of each ward was correlated with the land use types found therein. All of the correlations had p-values (0.408, 0.267, 0.715 and 0.484) which were greater than 0.05, hence the correlations though positively correlated were statistically insignificant and might have been a chanced occurrence. On the other hand, significant relationships were found between socio-economic characteristics of respondents and land use characterization in the study area. This implies that urban planning should be more homocentric as it has been established that the socioeconomic characteristics of the population is a more potent driver than the population numbers. The paper recommends that the National population commission should always publish the socio-economic characteristics of the population along with the census figures as this will aid in planning that will reflect the needs of the people.

Keywords: Land Use, Population and Sustainable Development.

a) Introduction

Land use/cover change refers to the transformation of the Land's surface and water bodies, influenced by a complex interplay of natural processes and human activities. Land use includes both the technique used to change the biophysical characteristics of the land and the motivation behind such manipulations (Etim *et al.*, 2023). The extent of land use change varies with time, location, type of land cover, and ongoing anthropogenic activity. A region's land use pattern results from natural and socioeconomic causes as well as human exploitation of natural resources over time and space (Etuk, 2021). It is also acknowledged that changes in land use are indicators of socioeconomic transformation and its underlying logics (Faye *et al.*, 2022). According to Etim (2021) and Wawonyi (2012), population dynamics play a crucial role in determining changes in land use and land cover. While population growth is a key driver of development, it can also have a significant negative impact on the environment when it exceeds the ecosystem's carrying capacity. It should come as no surprise that population is a factor considered when determining land use efficiency, as stated by Sustainable Development Goal 13.1. (Cai *et al.*, 2020). This paper thus sets out to assess the relationship between land use characterizations and population dynamics in Ikot Ekpene Local government Area, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

b) Literature Review

The urban population's wants and desires drive the demand for land resources. This is because the pattern of land use in any given location is highly influenced by the characteristics of that area's population. Typically, urban growth is followed by the modification of the natural landscape at the point of human population concentration. Nagdeve (2002) observed that population growth leads to expanding human settlements and increasing demand for food, fuel, and building materials. The unsustainable expansion of human needs leads to habitat destruction and loss of biodiversity. The effect of population on land use characterization in Mumbai Metropolitan, India between 1971 and 2011 was investigated by Kumar *et al.* (2014). The result of the study showed that the increase in the areal extent of the built up area happened at the detriment of agricultural land, forest land and wetland. The areas in different classes of land use were analyzed by superimposing the map of 2011 on the map of 1991 and 1971. It was observed that with the densification of the land at the city center and the suburbs, other parts of the metropolitan region experienced a faster growth rate. Due to the growing population pressure, the total built up area increased from 4.9% in 1971 to 12% in 1991. The population-land-use link was visualized by creating isopleth maps for 1971 and 1991 and superimposing them on the land-use map. The isopleth map revealed a substantial relationship between population growth and land use change. Alfred *et al.* (2016) discovered a favorable relationship between population and built-up areas in Niger State's Suleja LGA. The predicted population of the area for 1980, 2000, and 2015 were correlated against the areal extents of the built up area for the three years, and the relationship was graphically depicted. Digha *et al.* (2018)

explored the association between population and land use categorization in Calabar metropolitan. A Pearson product correlation analysis was performed on the city's population and built-up area for the years 2000, 2010, and 2014. The correlation coefficient was determined to be 0.85, indicating a positive association between population and land use categorization. The t-test revealed that the calculated value, 15.023, was bigger than the table value, 4.303, at the 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis was rejected, whereas the alternative hypothesis was supported, confirming that there was a strong association between population and land use pattern.

Wanyonyi (2012) investigated the relationship between population and land use changes in Kenya's Lugari District. The district's land cover was detected and classified using four land sat satellite images (1973 MSS, 1988TM, 2003ETM, and 2010 ETM+). For the four epochs, the population of the area was projected and correlated with the amount of built-up area. The results showed a substantial positive connection with 95% confidence. The report proposed that the carrying capacity of the ecosystem be assessed, environmental regulations be enforced, and afforestation be encouraged. Opatoyinbo *et al.* (2015) evaluated the relationship between population and land use categorization along the Kaduna flood plain of the River Kaduna. The study included predicted demographic data for each community, remote sensing technology, and a geographical information system, and it lasted from 1976 to 2010. Population was not found to be positively linked with land use pattern along the river flood plain. A graph was created to depict the relationship between population growth and land use patterns in the area; the graph revealed an ever-increasing tendency in population growth while the land use pattern moved on a downward trend. The study showed that there was no relationship between population changes and changes in urban land usage. According to Young *et al.* (1991), population increase is not the main driving force of land use change because its importance is relative to the other forces creating land use change, such as technological and social developments that improve people's living standards. Young *et al.* (1991) discovered no substantial link between land use patterns and population estimates on a global scale. They believe that while population density can generate changes in land use patterns, it is not a required driver of such changes. Karsidi (2004) also observed that substantial connections between land use pattern and population can be identified only when the study is limited to regions with similar socio-environmental parameters.

By way of summary, two patterns of analysis can be deciphered, one being time-series correlation of population figures with areal extent of land uses, and the other is the correlation of population figures with areal extent of land uses spatially. By analyzing data over time, it is almost probable that a positive relationship between built-up areas and population growth will be established as demonstrated by Wanyonyi (2012), Kumar *et al.* (2014), Alfred *et al.* (2016), and Digha *et al.* (2018). When data is collected on a spatial scale, however, it is likely that population will not be significantly connected with built-up regions, as discovered by Young *et al.* (1991), Karsidi (2004), Opatoyinbo *et al.* (2015), and Etim (2021).

c) The Concept of Sustainable Development

Sustainable development is the ability to advance the quality of human life while living within the carrying capacity of the supporting ecosystems (Daniel and Nwawo, 2018). Development is only viewed as positive if it makes human life better in all aspects; its environment inclusive. Sustainable development is defined as "Development that meets the needs of current generation without compromising the ability of the future generation to meet their own needs and aspirations (Drexhage and Murphy, 2010, Mfon and Etim, 2023). Sustainability can be viewed from many aspects such as technical sustainability (balanced demand and supply, no mining); financial sustainability (cost recovery); social sustainability (stability of population, stability of demand, willingness to pay); economic sustainability (sustaining economic development or welfare and production); institutional sustainability (capacity to plan, manage and operate the system); and Environmental sustainability. Sustainability appears to be a more complex and thus more difficult to handle, that is connected with adaptive management, biodiversity, ecological integrity and resilience rather than with policy, elitism or an accent on economy (Ivo and Etim, 2023).

d) Study Area

Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area is located within Latitudes 5°10' to 5° 30' North of the Equator and Longitudes 7° 30' to 7° 45' East of the Greenwich Meridian. It lies on the North western flank of Akwa Ibom State. It is bounded in the north and west by Obot Akara Local Government Area, in the east by Ikono Local Government Area and in the south by Essien Udim Local Government Area (Akpabio, 2010). Its position makes it one of the economic gateways to Akwa Ibom State. Ikot Ekpene is the political and cultural capital of Annang ethnic group. It is historic in local government administration in Nigeria, as it became a premier model local

government administrative centre in 1951. Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area has a land mass of 128km². The topography of the area is generally fairly flat. It has an elevation of about 60.96m (2090ft) above sea level. It has a very good run –off of storm water during and after rainfall. Its sand belongs to the undulating sandy plain classification. The soil of Ikot Ekpene forms part of the consolidated alluvial deposits of the late tertiary age, they are ferralitic in nature; meaning that it has high iron contents but have low minerals. It is stable, brownish, porous, acidic, and highly leached. Ikot Ekpene Local Government falls within the tropics and thus enjoys a humid tropical climate with mean rainfall of 2311mm, temperature of 28⁰C, relative humidity range of 70 to 80 %, and high precipitation of 250mm per annum. The population figures of Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area base on the 2006 population census was 141,408 persons (NPC, 2006). This Local government area is habited mainly by the Annang ethnic group.

Fig 1. Map of Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area

e) Research Methodology

Based on the prior knowledge of the study area and a brief reconnaissance survey of the study area, a classification scheme was developed for the study area. The land use type was classified in to four classes namely; built up areas, forested areas, cultivated areas and water bodies using supervised classification module in ARCGIS 10.1. Ikot Ekpene LGA is made up of 11 political wards, the population of the villages making up each political ward in Ikot Ekpene LGA were summed together and projected from 1991 to 2020 using the compound formula, with a growth rate of 2.83%, and this was used as the ward population. Likewise the land use map of the study area for 2020 was demarcated into political wards, and the areal extent of land uses in each ward was calculated. Questionnaires were administered to 400 respondents in the study area, this figure was arrived at using the Taro Yamane formulae for sample size determination. The population of each ward and socio-economic characteristics of respondents (income, household size, and occupation) were correlated with the areal extent of different land uses (water bodies, thick forest, built up area and cultivated farmland) in each ward. This was done for the eleven wards making up the study area; this analysis was done with the aid of SPSS Software using the Pearson product correlation analysis modules.

f) Results and Discussions

The land use map of Ikot Ekpene LGA was characterized into four categories; water bodies, thick forest, cultivated farmlands and built up areas. It was further demarcated into eleven political wards (see appendix i) and the areal

coverage of each land use type in the ward was calculated and correlated against its projected population figures. Dataset for the Pearson correlation is as shown on table 1.

Table 1 Table showing Land use classes and population of each ward

Ward	Population (In numbers)	Water Body (Km ²)	Thick Forest (Km ²)	Built-up Area (Km ²)	Cultivated Farmland (Km ²)
1	29345	0.040	3.675	4.153	3.007
2	13395	0.043	3.143	8.109	4.032
3	13075	0.046	1.831	3.432	2.179
4	19801	0.219	2.508	8.416	3.579
5	22325	1.200	2.566	5.466	2.976
6	21778	0.447	2.110	4.635	2.782
7	17286	0.041	1.918	4.837	2.610
8	20365	0.407	1.008	9.072	1.643
9	10602	0.021	2.360	2.759	2.184
10	15642	0.047	3.905	5.055	3.746
11	25389	0.051	5.134	5.591	4.495
Total	209001	2.562	30.158	61.529	33.231

Source: 2022 population Projection, LandSat Image Calculations.

From the Pearson product moment correlation carried out, population growth was found to be positively correlated with all the land uses. The correlation coefficient of 0.278 was found between population and water bodies, meaning that 7.73% of the variation in water bodies across the study area can be attributed to population growth, 0.267 correlation coefficient was found between population and thick forest, in other words 7.13% variations in the area of thick forest is associated with population growth, that between built up areas and population had a correlation coefficient of 0.118 inferring that 1.39% of variations in the area of built up areas across the political wards of Ikot Ekpene LGA can be explained by population growth. The correlation between cultivated farmland and population growth had a coefficient of 0.125 which adduces 1.56% changes in the area of cultivated farmland in the area to population growth.

Pearson Correlation Analysis results

		Water body	Thick Forest	Built-up Area	Cultivated Farmland
Population	Pearson	.278	.367	.125	.237
	Correlation	.408	.267	.715	.484
	Sig(2-tailed)				
	N	11	11	11	11

Source: Correlation results from SPSS (2023)

It is not said here that population size causes these changes but it is merely associated with it. All of the correlations had p-values (0.408, 0.267, 0.715 and 0.484) which were greater than 0.05, hence the correlations though positively correlated were statistically insignificant and might have been a chance occurrence. This has led to the acceptance of the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between population and land use characterization in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area. This is in tandem with the research of Opatoyinbo *et al.* (2015) which concluded that there was no correlation between population growth and urban land use changes. Young *et al.* (1991) also noted that population size is not the main driving force of land use change as its importance is relative to the other forces generating land use change such as technology and social advances that improve the conditions of life, they opined that population density may be sufficient to cause land use change but it is not a necessary driver for such changes.

The relationship between socio-economic characteristics of respondents and land use characterization in the study area was examined (see appendix i), it was found that income levels, occupation, educational status and household size had a significant correlation of 0.788, 0.638, 0.766 and -0.631 respectively with the built up areas. Karsidi (2004) noted that significant correlations between land uses and population growth can be found

only if the investigation is restricted to regions possessing similar socio-environmental characteristics or when measurements are done on a temporal rather than spatial scale. The contribution of population to land use change can be inferred by studying the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents and not just by looking at population in terms of numbers.

g) Conclusion and Recommendations

Land use change is driven by the interaction in space and time between biophysical and human dimension, moreover, there are also the potential impacts on physical and social dimensions. Its impact on soil often occurs creeping, that land managers hardly contemplate initiating ameliorative or counterbalance measures. Poor land management has degraded vast amounts of land, reduced our ability to produce enough food, and is a major threat to rural livelihoods in different parts of the world especially in developing countries. It has been empirically proven that mere increase in number of people does not cause land use change but rather the socio-economic characteristics of the said population. This implies that urban planning should be homocentric, knowing the socio economic characteristics of the people will aid in better planning little wonder public participation is always advocated for. Government should make sure that the socio economic data of residents should be aggregated and published during census exercise; this will go a long way to help the town planners to produce more people oriented plans. Decentralisation of facilities should be done; this will ensure that the neighbouring local Government areas are provided with adequate and functional facilities to discourage rural urban migration into Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area which currently serves both as senatorial and ethnic headquarters.

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Appendix I

2022 Land Use/Cover map of Ikot Ekpene LGA showing political wards

APPENDIX II

Pearson Product Correlation Analysis Results

		Population	Income	House Hold Size	Education level	Occupation	Water body	Thick forest	Built-up area	Cultivated farmland
Population	Pearson Correlation	1	-.125	-.024	-.051	.404	.287	.367	.125	.237
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.714	.945	.883	.218	.392	.267	.715	.484
	N	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11
Income	Pearson Correlation	-.125	1	-.636*	.786**	.467	-.132	.000	.788**	.245
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.714		.035	.004	.148	.699	1.000	.004	.467
	N	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11
Household size	Pearson Correlation	-.024	-.636*	1	-.518	-.641*	.270	.053	-.631*	-.228
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.945	.035		.103	.034	.422	.878	.037	.500
	N	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11
Education level	Pearson Correlation	-.051	.786**	-.518	1	.703*	.075	-.107	.766**	.115
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.883	.004	.103		.016	.825	.754	.006	.737
	N	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11
Occupation	Pearson Correlation	.404	.467	-.641*	.703*	1	.200	.199	.638*	.397
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.218	.148	.034	.016		.555	.557	.034	.227
	N	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11
Water body	Pearson Correlation	.287	-.132	.270	.075	.200	1	-.269	.174	-.168
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.392	.699	.422	.825	.555		.424	.608	.621
	N	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11
Thick forest	Pearson Correlation	.367	.000	.053	-.107	.199	-.269	1	-.141	.859**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.267	1.000	.878	.754	.557	.424		.680	.001
	N	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11
Built-up area	Pearson Correlation	.125	.788**	-.631*	.766**	.638*	.174	-.141	1	.205
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.715	.004	.037	.006	.034	.608	.680		.546
	N	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11
Cultivated farmland	Pearson Correlation	.237	.245	-.228	.115	.397	-.168	.859**	.205	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.484	.467	.500	.737	.227	.621	.001	.546	
	N	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11

SPSS Extract, 2023

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).